

EXPLORING THE COMPOSITIONAL DIVERSITY OF LUNAR PLAGIOCLASES WITH VNIR REFLECTANCE SPECTROSCOPY: INSIGHTS FROM SYNTHETIC EXPERIMENTAL SAMPLES.

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Introduction: Plagioclase is the most abundant mineral in the lunar highlands, as evidenced by returned samples, meteorites and remote sensing [1]. Visible Near-InfraRed (VNIR) reflectance signatures of plagioclase, characterized by a diagnostic absorption band centered around 1.25 μm caused by Fe^{2+} incorporation in the crystal structure [2], were identified on the Moon's surface with high spatial and spectral resolution imaging spectrometers aboard the SELENE and Chandrayaan-1 spacecrafts [e.g., 3, 4]. Such spectra detected in well-exposed outcrops (e.g., craters walls or central peaks) are generally interpreted as pure anorthosites (PAN) based on both the absence of mafic mineral spectral features and the strength of the 1.25 μm absorption. This assumption has notable limitations, especially since the plagioclase band intensity primarily reflects the iron concentration rather than the mineral abundance in the rock [5]. Moreover, contrary to the belief that plagioclase is only spectrally visible when the mafic component is $< 10\%$ [6], new laboratory studies showed that its signature can be predominant in various other rock types besides anorthosite (plagioclase-phyric basalt, dacite, granodiorite, granite) with plagioclase content as low as 18% and compositions ranging from An_{37} to An_{56} [7]. These results suggest that some lunar plagioclase VNIR signatures could belong to more sodic feldspar-bearing rocks, as supported by the recent spectral detection of alkalic plagioclase in Aristarchus crater [8], and the identification of a new mechanism for albitic feldspar generation in the Na-depleted lunar environment [9].

Thus, defining clear trends and quantitative relationships between the plagioclase VNIR spectral properties and its chemical composition is crucial to understand past and future detections of lunar plagioclase signatures. In this work, we investigate the effect of Ca/Na content and Fe concentration on the 1.25 μm absorption band of this mineral. For that purpose, we synthesize experimental samples of well-controlled compositions, free of the weathering or phase mixing effects observed in the spectra of terrestrial analogs [7], to acquire reference plagioclase spectra.

Samples & Methods: Reagent-grade oxides (CaCO_3 , Na_2O , Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , Fe_2O_3 and MgO) were mixed and homogenized in a muffle furnace for the following synthesis of Fe-enriched plagioclases with different compositions (individually varying Ca/Na and Fe contents). Small pellets of the resulting starting glass materials were hung on platinum wire

loops and subjected to initial heating above liquidus temperature followed by dynamic crystallization experiments in a vertical furnace (1 atm). Runs were conducted under different redox conditions controlled by CO-CO₂ gas mixtures in order to obtain varying iron oxidation state ratios. Since all iron in plagioclase is Fe^{2+} below the Fayalite-Magnetite-Quartz – FMQ buffer [10], experiments under such $f\text{O}_2$ values are of particular interest for applications to the highly reducing lunar environment. The heating protocol and cooling steps were fine-tuned to optimize the formation of large crystals ($> 32 \mu\text{m}$, which is the spatial resolution of the laboratory spectral camera). In a few runs (sodic endmembers), high pressure was needed for optimal crystal growth; a piston-cylinder apparatus (1 GPa) was then operated using either platinum or graphite capsules (depending on the target redox conditions) as material holders.

In order to avoid transparency-related contributions from the quenched glass to the plagioclase VNIR signature, the ideal sample preparation protocol requires the run products to be polished on both sides for isolation of single crystals. Characterization is then performed with both the optical and electron (SEM) microscopes, while VNIR reflectance spectra are measured with a HySpex SWIR-640 hyperspectral microimaging camera (0.96–2.5 μm spectral range with a 32 μm spatial resolution and a 4.38 nm spectral resolution) allowing for grain-by-grain analyses of the synthetic samples. Data are converted to reflectance using a white reference panel and further analyzed with the IDL/ENVI software.

Results & Discussion: Millimetric anorthite crystals ($\sim\text{An}_{93-97}$) with various Fe-enrichments were successfully synthesized under two redox states: in oxidizing conditions at ambient air vs. at $f\text{O}_2$ values between \sim FMQ and FMQ-2. Runs with intermediate compositions yield zoned plagioclases ($\sim\text{An}_{50-80}$) large enough (on the order of several hundred μm) to investigate the influence of chemical zonations on the mineral spectral properties. The synthesis of sodic plagioclases (Ab_{100}) $> 25 \mu\text{m}$ in size was seemingly limited at 1 atm by the viscosity of the parent anhydrous albitic melts preventing chemical diffusion. 1-GPa experiments were then effective in growing larger crystals reaching 300 μm , as increasing pressure lowers the viscosity of these compositions [11]. However, precise $f\text{O}_2$ control in the piston-cylinder apparatus for runs targeting redox conditions below FMQ proves to be difficult and requires more work.

VNIR spectra of both glass and crystal phases extracted from an anorthite-rich sample are shown in Fig. 1. The associated plagioclase composition is $\sim\text{An}_{97}$ with $\text{FeO} \sim 0.07$ wt% occurring mostly as Fe^{2+} since the source experiment $f\text{O}_2$ values fall in between FMQ+0.05 and FMQ-0.24. The quenched glass exhibits a VNIR signature typical of iron-bearing silicate glasses with two major absorption bands centered around 1.05 and 1.9 μm [12] while the anorthite displays a plagioclase-characteristic absorption feature ca. 1.2 μm . The absence of a second glass-related band at 1.9 μm in the studied crystal spectrum indicates minimal-to-no phase mixing, which attests to the purity of this synthetic plagioclase VNIR signature. Owing to the camera's spectral range, the spectra of both sample constituents lack the left shoulder of their first absorption band, making it difficult to calculate some of the typical spectral parameters (band depth, center, ...). The analyses are further complicated by the necessity to remove the continuum in lunar spectra, with various methods being proposed in the literature and often resulting in slight shifts in band center position estimates [e.g., 13]. Fig. 1 presents both raw and continuum-removed spectra obtained with the ENVI convex hull algorithm. In our continuum-free synthetic plagioclase spectrum, the absorption band center position (~ 1.17 μm) does compare with the one from PAN orbital detections in Humboldt crater (~ 1.19 μm). In the continuum-free glass spectrum, the first-band center position (~ 1.13 μm) is rather different than the expected value (1.05 μm). Whether this variation is caused by phase chemistry (Fe content, speciation) or by the continuum removal processing is to be further investigated.

Future work: Additional reflectance spectra will be acquired with the HySpex VNIR-3000 N instrument, a camera operating in the visible spectral range (0.4–1 μm), to measure the left shoulder of absorption bands near 1.1 μm . Continuum removal and data processing will be optimized to derive reliable spectral parameters from the spectra of all synthetic samples. Combined with upcoming electron microprobe (EPMA) quantitative geochemical analyses and $\mu\text{-XAS}$ characterization of the iron speciation, our unique spectral library acquired on fully characterized synthetic samples will shed light on the significance of plagioclase detections on planetary surfaces with VNIR reflectance spectroscopy.

Figure 1: VNIR reflectance spectra of the anorthite (in blue) and glass (in grey) phases from a synthetic sample (details in the text) averaged on 5×5 -pixels regions. Lighter curves are unprocessed spectra while darker curves are the same spectra after continuum removal with ENVI. A pure anorthosite (PAN) VNIR continuum-free detection captured by the M^3 imaging spectrometer aboard Chandrayaan-1 in Humboldt crater [13] is shown in red for comparison. Band centers are marked with double arrows and their shift from raw spectra to continuum-free spectra is highlighted by shaded areas of corresponding color.

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